

Management of Information Systems Resources in Digital Organizations for On-Line, Real-Time Responsiveness

Author Details: Dimitrios Stamoulis

Abstract

Information systems (IS) resources are managed within an IT governance framework that is both a regulatory requirement for several industry sectors, as well as a necessity for managing the most expensive resources in an organization, which are IS related. However, IT governance frameworks lean against the traditional hierarchical control organizational structures and are not configured for digital value chain models with flat organizational designs. This paper investigates the implications of the demand for on-line, real-time responsiveness of contemporary digital organizations on the management of IS resource and on the applicability of IT governance frameworks, based on relevant current research literature as well as on twenty interviews with managers of such organizations.

Keywords: *IS resources, digital organizations, IT governance, digital value chains*

Introduction

“Between faster computers, better software and bigger data, ours is the first era in human history in which technology is constantly accelerating.[...] Technology, he argues, is developing at an increasing, exponential rate. But human society – from our businesses to our political institutions – can only ever adapt at a slower, incremental pace. The result is an 'exponential gap' – between the power of new technology and humans' ability to keep up.¹” Technological change and innovations are being implemented at accelerating speeds. Every new invention, gradual or radical, takes much time to market, thus the evolution is exponential. Azhar(2021) argued that despite the exponential change of technological evolution, changes and adaptations in society, organizations and the economy are linear. Thus the exponential gap: “the chasm between new forms of technology – along with the fresh approaches to businesses, work, politics and civil society they bring about – and the corporations, employees, politics, and wider social norms that get left behind”. (ibid, Preface). This gap represents the painful transformation that organizations need to undergo in order to become digital ones and reap the benefits of new technologies, whose evolution pace is exponential.

In this paper, we use Michael Porter’s Value Chain Model to present the digital transformation of all the main activities in contemporary organizations, in order to show the multitude of technologies and the complexity of IT-based operations for organizations aiming at reacting to the external environment on-line, real-time. However, running and reacting in digital speeds, requires not only appropriate IT architectures but also appropriate management of IS resources within an IT framework that is compatible with the new design of digital organizations.

Digital value chains

Back in 1985, Michael Porter (2008) introduced the concept of a value chains as a way to explain how business processes combine and cooperate in order to enable value addition that allows them to add a margin to the cost of the product or service, and, thus survive financially. He proposed two basic set of business processes: the primary ones (inbound logistics, operations, outbound logistics, marketing and sales and service and the support ones (firm infrastructure, human resources management, technology development and procurement). Once manually performed, these value chain tasks are now IT-enabled and operate on-line, real-time, partially or fully automated.

Starting from primary activities, in-bound and out-bound logistics represent all the material and immaterial flows that cross the organizational perimeter in the form of an offering that carries some added value for those destined to. Digital links to upper and lower bounds of the supply chain include e-procurement solutions and platforms, e-sales solutions, e-buying / purchasing and e-selling correspondingly. Platforms and solutions abandon, but the visible part of them is only a smart part of the digital value chain. The

¹ [Exponential by Azeem Azhar \(exponential-book.com\)](https://www.exponential-book.com/)

essence behind these, lies into the integration with the internal systems of the organization, such as accounting, warehouse stocking, purchasing, etc. as well as the automatic purchase placement, ordering, reconciliation of payments etc. These components within interorganizational business processes allowing information and digital goods to flow and synchronize the operations between and among the transacting parts. "Tactical and operations interventions for value chain integration lead to enhancement of efficiency and effectiveness of the value chain. However, the strategic decision on the mode of the integration/relationship between the value chain partners can strongly influence the success of the Value Chain itself." [Ilyas et. al., 2007] The tighter the integration / relationship, the deeper the use of intelligent systems that implement the digital integration, which rely on application programming interfaces (APIs) through which interoperability can be achieved. Using API-based integration to connect in one-to-one or one-to-many relationships through platforms, organizations participate into digital ecosystems, whose business value is more than the sum of its parts, as it happens in the networked economy. [Valdez-De-Leon, 2019] Digitalizing the in-bound and out-bound logistics based on intelligent systems, from simple decision making algorithms to experts systems and artificial intelligence, an excellent balance between supply and demand can be achieved; this balance or even optimization has always been an objective for the supply chain management. [Altken, 1999] Achieving the on-demand supply chain [Chen and Paulraj, 2004] using digital intelligent systems creates the ultimate efficiency and effectiveness for in-bound and out-bound logistics. In between them, the production process, depending on the type of the industry and the produced good or service, is fully IT-dependent nowadays for data processing, control and decision support.

Operations are heavily transformed in many industry sectors, with robots (hardware) and robotic process automation (RPA software) replacing humans in repetitive, non-cognitive business rules manual tasks. [Murray, 2017] RPA tools are supervised by humans to increase dramatically efficiency and effectiveness in middle- and back-office operations in any industry and in many functions, such as underwriting, records-updating, accounting, human resources, etc. [Aguirre & Rodriguez, 2017], [Fung, 2014]. Therefore, digitization is of paramount importance in producing value in the area of operations, even more now that artificial intelligence is getting more embedded in RPA software in an effort to cover cognitive tasks of business processes as well. [Martínez-Rojas, et. al., 2021]

Finally, marketing and service which are also part of the primary activities of the value chain business model, rely heavily on technologies such as big data analytics, omni-channel customer experience and communication, as well as service support using bots, voice recognition and synthesis, etc. in contemporary digital industries. "Since early 2015 there has been a visible advantage in the focus on digital marketing and advertising over traditional channels. In general, marketers have been reducing their budgets for traditional advertising, while growth in expenses on digital marketing remained positive. In February 2021, CMOs in the U.S said that their digital spending grew by 14.3 percent, relative to preceding 12 months."²

Regarding support activities of the value chain model, namely firm infrastructure, human resources management, technology development and procurement, they have been heavily impacted by IT tools and digital methods of work. Take for example the recruitment process in the human resources management area. It used to take weeks to receive CVs after the publication of a job vacancy post, read them all and select the most appropriate ones for a face-to-face interview. Whereas, the new digital process is based, for example, on criteria that the recruiter is setting-up in linkedin for a first round of selection to get automatically completed and rank the rest of the CVs in relevant importance according to the education, experience and skills criteria. Digital platforms like these that take stock of the crowd-sourcing element (since everyone contributes freely his/her own CV) and perform immediately, at a click of a button, an once strenuous task, are paradigm shifts in the methods of work which have become online, real-time.

Technology development has moved from months- to daily-releases of new software and pure digital products. IT is more and more organized in agile teams following the principles of the agile manifesto³ and

² <https://www.statista.com/statistics/693449/digital-vs-traditional-marketing-budget-change-according-to-cmos-usa/>

³ <https://agilemanifesto.org/>

methodologies like Scrum are becoming popular for rapid, value-based prioritization and gradual implementation of functional parts of the IT artifacts.

The digitization of the entire value chain has created the ability of digital organizations to respond on-line, real-time to almost all kinds of internal and external stimuli. More examples of digital applications for digital organizations can be found, for example, in Westerman et. al. (2014) However, this demand for immediate responsiveness puts tremendous pressure of IT governance structures and process in order to ensure that information systems resources are managed appropriately so that they can maximize value production for digital organizations.

IS resources management

Designing a digital organization is not an easy task. Research results from over 150 organizations have identified “a core set of organizational characteristics (including mindsets, practices and resources) that underpin enterprise development of Digital Capability to improve customer experience, internal operations or employee engagement. We introduce the concept of Digital Dexterity, the sustained organizational ability to rapidly adapt and self-organize to take advantage of emerging digital possibilities, and show that these same organizational characteristics are associated with digital dexterity.” [Soule et. al., 2016] This research concludes that “in order to build an enterprise for long term digital advantage, executives need to cultivate the unique set of characteristics of a Digital Organization that collectively enable both Digital Capability and Digital Dexterity.” [ibid]

In the context of the IT function, these two characteristics, digital capability and digital dexterity, correspond to IT Agility and IT ambidexterity. According to Leonhardt et. al., (2017) “IT function plays a major role in supporting digitization initiatives. First, our study finds IT agility to positively influence the IT function’s digitization support. Thus, IT functions that are able to sense relevant developments and to act accordingly are best suited to produce digital innovation. Furthermore, we found that IT ambidexterity has a moderating effect on this relationship, suggesting that IT functions need to be able to experiment with new technologies, while at the same time efficiently and effectively refining their current IT resources to best utilize their capabilities in the agility dimensions sensing and responding for digitization.”

How information systems resources should be managed by an agile and ambidexterious IT function so as to enable to capability and dexterity to digital organizations? Have the IT governance frameworks to be revised in order to respond to such new requirements?

First of all, information systems resources belong to three categories: human resources, business processes/organizational architecture and information technology.

In the area of human resources, we observe that digital organizations are training both business and IT staff to agile methods of work, upgrading their skills to new IT tools in the areas of personal organization (such as MS-planner, Kanban type of dashboards for to-do/completed/paused work, etc.), to new digital marketing methods (such as on-line focus groups, online personas design, net promoter scoring, beta version measurement of customer satisfaction etc.), to group-based innovation culture mentality. Performance assessment for staff is shifting from personal to group performance, from qualitative to quantitative types of metrics, from stability of behavior to innovation contribution etc.

In the area of business processes, product and process owners are urged to document their workflows, their process maps with process mapping tools, to identify areas for robotics process automation and to cooperate with IT in order to orchestrate their tasks over business process management (BPM) platforms. [Hammer, 2015] Business people need to be able to communicate with IT over business process maps, use low-code/no-code tools as substitutes for expensive, lengthy projects that would reengineer existing IT applications for interoperability and the contribute to data governance procedures as data stewards and editors of the corporate data dictionary. Tight data governance is a prerequisite for big data analytics and

meaning analytics results, otherwise data may have different scope, meaning and usage within different organizational sub-contexts, and, thus, produce meaningless and confusing analytics results.

In the area of IT, technological resources are reconfigured to allow for servitization [Birgersson & Granath, 2018], by containerizing existing software modules to be offered as service blocks to new software constructions. In this way, technological resources are organized as an array of modules/ building blocks with front-end applications and back-end (APIs) services to allow for easy integration, plug-and-play type of application development and deployment, since the on-line, real-time responsiveness requirements need to be met. Therefore, APIs are being used for internal purposes, for partners (business to business) solutions, for public / open use by external partners and developers. According to McKinsey⁴, their use for internal purposes aims for cost reduction, for partners' aims at API monetization, enhanced security and partner costs reduction and for the public aims at innovation through community engagement and extended market reach.

Managing the IS resources differently to enable on-line, real-time responsiveness, is obviously a prerequisite for the digital transformation of organizations. IT governance is not irrelevant but rather affected by the design architecture of digital organizations. In these, "actor-oriented principles and designs can be used to organize and perform activities. Actor-oriented digital organizations are collaborative, agile, and minimally hierarchical. [...] Digital organizations need technologically aware and adept leaders who can set the digital agenda and create the context for the digitization of every relevant aspect of their organizations. Digitization is occurring at an accelerating pace; successful leaders need to synchronize their organizations to digital clock speed." [Snow et. al, 2017]

IT governance is both a regulatory requirement and a necessity for deriving value from IT investments as well as a tool to manage supply and demand of IT resources. However, IT governance relies on rules, structured decision making, implicit hierarchical procedures, strict reporting & monitoring. Although proposals have been made on how to embed IT governance frameworks into the agile practice necessary for digital organizations [Verlaine et. al., 2015], [Verlaine et. al., 2016], it is still an open question how IT governance can be applied in such a new organizational design without hampering the on-line, real-time responsiveness nature of digital organizations.

After several interviews with managers from digital organizations in three sectors, (banking and finance, telecoms and health), the answer is apparently hidden within the essence of the organizational redesign that digital organizations undergo. Increased responsibility, accountability, empowerment and the similar qualities with which agile teams are bestowed in order to create the digital capacity and dexterity that qualifies them as digital ones, both for the business and IT functions, imply that IT governance needs to go deeper into the organization and become part of the agile teams responsibilities. IT governance and the smart use of IS resources is no longer a theme for high-level executives, nor a top-down approach for the alignment between IT and business plans. Strategy and planning derives bottom-up in digital organizations that have vested in innovation culture. Therefore, agile teams need to internalize and apply IT governance; they are also empowered to modify the framework lowering the IT governance responsibility from the C-level or even managers' level to agile teams' level.

If this is the case, then what's the role of managers? They own responsibility is to create the environment, the culture, and the appropriate field for allowing such agile teams to flourish and also to lead, coach, ensure and assess the production of business value through the digital value chains. In this vein, the aforementioned actor-theory which has been proposed as a design method for digital organizations fits well to the described purpose of empowering agile teams in order to use the IT governance framework as a tool for intelligent use of IS resources. Why it fits well? Because, "in an actor-oriented organization, actors understand the overall structure and processes of the organization, and their decisions and actions are taken in pursuit of the

⁴ www.mckinsey.com/industries/financial-services/our-insights/data-sharing-and-open-banking

organization's common good. By focusing on the common good, actors can take advantage of shared values, norms of reciprocity, and trust in the self-governance process." [Snow et. al., 2017].

If the tasks of an IT governance framework, such as prioritization, budgeting, cost and resources allocation, quality monitoring, data governance etc. is assigned as a responsibility to agile teams to apply, modify and run, then it is questionable whether it still remains a corporate policy framework or it diminishes in a fragmented set of practices with decentralized decisions taken by the agile teams. Although decentralization is obvious, IT governance as an overarching set of principle to manage IS resources is still valid and necessary. Managers need to ensure homogeneity and appropriateness; for example different reporting styles should be able to be consolidated into a homogeneous total picture that is communicable, meaningful and actionable by the top management.

Conclusions

"A modern value chain [...] is a business system that creates end-user satisfaction and realizes the objectives of other member stakeholders". [Walters & Lancaster, 2000] When value chains become digital, they are characterized by on-line, real-time responsiveness to internal and external stimuli. Such behavior poses more requirements for smart and effective management of IS resources and the overall question of how an IT governance can be applied and executed in a digital organization. Using contemporary research literature as well as the material from twenty interviews of managers that work with or within digital organizations, this paper concludes that IT governance frameworks must be revised to allow for ownership by the agile teams that run the digital organization in a mentality that follows the collaborative, self-organizing actors paradigm. IT governance is a key component of corporate governance; it can't and shouldn't be abolished. Instead, IT governance and the subsequent IS resources' management for digital value creation must be part of the "design for self-organization rather than [...] hierarchical mechanisms for control and coordination." [Snow, et. al, 2017].

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